

How to light-touch review:

Guidance for Liaison partners

This guideline describes what is expected from each LIAISON partner with regard to the Light-touch Review (LTR). Please read this document very carefully in preparation of the light touch reviews. It deals with both methodological and conceptual as with very practical issues .

LIAISON aims

LIAISON aims to make a significant and meaningful contribution to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. Researchers, policy advisors, actors from interactive innovation projects, initiatives and networks, farm/forestry advisors, decision makers and administrators are jointly investigating the design and implementation of interactive project approaches.

The light-touch review aims:

FROM THE CALL TEXT

In the original call text it is stressed that proposals should investigate the design and implementation of interactive innovation projects on the basis of a substantial number of case studies in a broad range of agriculture and forestry sectors.

FROM THE DOA

The light-touch review aims to identify, collect and review 200 interactive innovation project approaches, and to interpret and present the information gathered. This will result in:

1. Valuable insights into the implementation of interactive innovation project approaches across Europe as the review will identify challenges, perceived failures and success stories
2. A strong basis for the selection of in-depth cases for WP 4 as such supporting the subsequent analysis in LIAISON

LIAISON partners: we need your help!

12 light-touch reviews per partner

- Each partner identified a list of about 20 projects (D3.1)
- Out of this list each partner needs to complete 12 light-touch reviews
- Some partners cover projects in neighbouring countries
- All LIAISON partners are asked to inform the T3.1 core-team* at the earliest opportunity which 12 projects they are proceeding with

* Andrew Fieldsend, Varga Eszter, Elke Rogge, Evelien Cronin and Katrina Ronningen

Methodology of the LTR

Combined methodology

For the light-touch review a **desk analysis** will be combined with a **semi-structured open interview**. As this is a light-touch review and time is limited, this interview will happen by means of a **telephone call** with one of the project leaders.

As we are working with a **semi-structured** approach, a **list of questions** is provided. We ask all LIAISON partners to provide answers to these questions as concisely and accurately as possible. This is important for the sake of the analysis and comparability. However, interviewers should also allow the interviewees the **opportunity to elaborate or to add information** according to their needs and let them talk freely about issues they find most important.

The estimated time of an interview is **about 1 hour**.

To complete the entire process of the LTR we propose to follow **4 major steps**. These steps are elaborated in the following slides.

General remarks

Before starting!

- Before you start you should **read through the entire list of questions**. This includes reading the questions for interpretation that only need to be answered after the one telephone call interview. If you know what is expected from you will be more confident to ask for clarification or to add some follow-up questions.
- **Not all projects are 'projects'**. We are well aware that not all cases will be 'projects' sensu strictu, they may be other initiatives that have evolved over time. For practical reasons however we are using the term 'project' throughout the list of questions. If you are dealing with another form of collaboration you can replace 'project' with 'network', 'partnership', 'initiative' or 'collaboration' and this will still make complete sense.

For each of the 12 cases the following 4 steps need to be completed

STEP 1

DESK ANALYSIS

Factual data are gathered through desk analysis searching for existing information e.g. project websites, brochures, publications, ... Contact persons are identified

STEP 2

ONE TELEPHONE CALL INTERVIEW

Conceptual information is gathered by means of a one telephone call interview with one of the key actors of the project. These questions serve the purpose of understanding the process the project has gone through

STEP 3

DATA INTERPRETATION

Based on the data gathered in the first two steps, the LIAISON researchers answer some additional questions that give a first interpretation of the gathered data

STEP 4

DATA GATHERING IN EXCEL TEMPLATE

The gathered data are added in a preformatted Excel template

Step 1: desk analysis

Empirical indicators

In this first section we will gather **factual information** about the project (name, duration, partners,...). These data do not leave room for interpretation. Much of this information can be obtained through an online desk search.

TIP: if there is some factual information that you cannot find through a desk search or that you have your doubts about, you can always check this information during the one telephone call interview.

Step 2: telephone call interview

Conceptual questions

Besides the factual information on the project the aim of the LTR is also to get a first insight into the implementation of interactive innovation project approaches across Europe. In order to obtain this insight during the telephone interview we will ask questions on the following topics:

- The project partnership
- Cooperation during the project
- Project performance
- Project outcomes
- Evaluation of the project

Throughout these questions we also probe for six analytical characteristics that have been described as important for innovation processes:

- Governance
- Knowledge and learning
- Institutions
- Networking
- Capacities and skills
- Enabling/policy environment

Step 3: data interpretation

Interpretation after the interview

The third step of the LTR incorporates a first step of analysis. The interviewer is in the best position to make a first interpretation of the data he/she has gathered. This step can happen after the one phone call interview. Some of the concepts that we want to use might not be common knowledge for the interviewees (eg. the innovation pathways and the innovation spiral). Within the timeframe of this interview we will not have the time to introduce these concepts to the interviewees. Therefore, we suggest the interviewer answers the questions in the third part of the Excel template based on his/her understanding and interpretation of the interview.

Step 4: data gathering in the Excel template

- The reporting template is largely self-explanatory
- Some parts can be filled out before the interview (e.g. the factual information) while other parts probably need to be filled out after the interview
- While it is probably best to conduct the interview in the native language of the interviewee, the template needs to be filled out in English!

Part B. Empirical indicators	
B.1	Project identifiers
B.1.1	Project name (if any)
B.1.1a	Project website
B.1.2	Start date
B.1.3	End date
B.1.4	Current status
B.1.5	Nationality of coordinator
B.1.6	Region (if relevant)
B.1.7	Domain
B.1.7.a	Sector
B.1.8	Topic of the project/short description (150 words max.)

- Beware that some questions work with a dropdown list! These questions are indicated in blue

- We believe that the reporting template is largely self-explanatory. However, in the following slides we give some additional explanation for questions that might not be entirely clear.

Clarifications

PART 1: Empirical indicators for the desk study

B.2.3	Cooperation type (please check the right box)	<input type="checkbox"/> FORMAL (if there is a signed document)	OR	<input type="checkbox"/> INFORMAL (all other cases)
B.2.3.a	Please select a cooperation type			

- **Formal:** if there is any type of signed document. This can be a consortium agreement, contract, code of conduct, product specifications,...
- **Informal:** all other types of cooperation for which there are no signed documents

B.2.4	Please describe how this project or partnership involves multi-actor co-creation of innovation (max. 50 - 100 words)
-------	--

- A **multi-actor partnership** consists of at least two or more entities. The LIAISON consortium interprets this term broadly. Some partnerships composed solely of, for example, farmers could be 'multi-actor', and the essential requirement is that the actors involved must have 'complementary types of knowledge' and/or different *functions* in the partnership.

Clarifications

PART 2: Telephone call interview

B.4.1

How was the project set up?
(max. 100-150 words)

This entails asking about:

- the initiator of the project
- the motivation for involvement
- bottom-up, top-down, a combination of both

B.4.3.a

How were partner organisations selected?
(max. 100-150 words)

This entails asking about:

- the multi-actor dimension
- diversity of knowledge
- parameters for selection
- History of cooperation (had they previously worked together?)

Tip: The questions in part 2 are inspired by the Innovation History Methodology. If you are interested you can find more information about this on Nexcloud

Clarifications

PART 2: Telephone call interview

D.3.1

What kind of information will/did you need to bring your project to a successful end?

This entails various types of data. For example, certain databases, technical information, marketing information, qualitative information,...

D.4.4

How do you evaluate the role of the policy environment in the success of your project?

This entails how government, policy and policy frameworks work; and this on all level ranging from the local to the European level.

Clarifications

PART 3: Further understanding about the project

In part 3 we ask the LIAISON partner to give a first interpretation of the data gathered in the interview.

Therefore we use concepts that have been introduced in WP1.

More specifically we refer to the four inter-related '**pathways for innovation support**' and to the **innovation spiral**. More information is given in the following slides.

Tip: more information can be found in the guidance template of T1.3

Clarifications

PART 3: Further understanding about the project – pathways for innovation support

Pathway 1: capturing, articulating and nurturing ‘new ideas’

Supporting or facilitating the identification, articulation and nurturing of promising ‘new ideas’ that may lead to innovation of whatever type. The three approaches commonly used for kicking-off the preliminary phases of an innovation process are:

1. bottom-up individual approach helping individuals with a ‘new idea’ to articulate and nurture it
2. bottom-up group approach bringing different stakeholders together to work in groups to identify, articulate and nurture ‘new ideas’
3. top-down approach involving some form of higher-level strategic planning and the identification of pre-defined priorities for innovation actions and/or innovation support.

Pathway 2: building the capacity of innovation actors

Pathway 2 is about building the capacity to innovate and is, in many circumstances (but not all), a result of Pathway 1. As the innovation process progresses, then the aspirations and needs of the innovation actors involved will evolve and grow. Pathway 2 ensures that concrete mechanisms are in place to help build the capacity of all participating actors (whether individuals, groups, businesses, institutions etc.) to get connected, to work together and self-organise, to co-create, to design and manage experiments, to run tests and to generally apply new ideas and approaches. Dedicated innovation support service providers (ISSPs) commonly play an important role in this pathway by providing access to a vast array of technical and other specific knowledge and skills, plus a range of services from basic training to more sophisticated innovation support such as the facilitation of iterative visioning or reflective learning cycles. Since co-creation is such an important part of the innovation process, basic capacity building may include match-making and the brokering of partnerships, plus the development and implementation of projects.

Pathway 3: dissemination and the embedding of effective innovations

Many actions / activities in Pathway 3 are not specific to the innovation process, but may involve a range of ‘standard’ techniques commonly associated with promoting good practice or the transfer / uptake of new technologies (e.g. classical farm advisory services). These are perfectly acceptable, but farmer decision-making and the adoption is actually influenced by a much greater range of factors. Depending upon national / regional context, it is also possible that a range of legal, financial and institutional factors will impact upon, or even block, the embedding or mainstreaming of innovations, some of which may be addressed directly by Pathway 4.

Pathway 4: improving the ‘enabling environment for innovation’

Pathway 4 concerns improving the enabling environment that frames and conditions the seven phases of the innovation process. This includes improving various enabling conditions, such as:

- institutional e.g. the policy/legislative environment which supports innovations
- procedural e.g. sources of flexible finance / simplified cost options to ease access to funding for innovation actions
- professional e.g. access to trainings to provide necessary skills and knowledge and means to facilitate / promote innovation
- organisational e.g. the possibility to interact with other partners willing to seek innovative solutions
- operational e.g. enabling transnational or cross-sector innovation
- technical e.g. adjusting legislation to supporting new techniques and technologies applicable in rural areas
- interactivity and complementarity e.g. promoting interaction / complementarity between different funding streams

Clarifications

PART 3: Further understanding about the project – innovation spiral

Case 2: Tikka Farm

New building design
Innovative feed wall
(Technological innovation)

The concept of the innovation spiral was introduced in the AgriSpin-project. It identifies seven stages in an innovation process:

- Initial idea
- Inspiration
- Planning
- Development
- Realisation
- Dissemination
- Embedding

This model allows for systematically ordering the observations in these stages of the innovation process. It also stimulates analytical questions for understanding why things happened as they did. However, we must be aware that using this model does not steer our observations so that they would fit into the stages (Wielinga et al., 2017).

Tip: The figure on the left gives an idea of how it can be used. For more information we refer to the analytical framework of AgriSpin and to Wielinga et al., 2017.

From: Wielinga et al., 2017

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 652642

Practicalities

We are GDPR compliant if:

- We collect identifying information which are **not the names of the people** interviewed, but only:
 - their role in the project and
 - the type of partner organisation
- We collect **the names of the projects for our information** in the template, but **anonymise the compiled database** when we are conducting the analysis by assigning codes to the original data gathering templates
- We ask for **“informed consent” orally** at the start of the phone call (both informed on what will happen with the data collected + whether or not they will be recorded)
- If you prefer to work with a written consent, this is also possible. A template has been elaborated as a part of D

TIP: you could this formulation “Thank you for agreeing with this interview and for it to be recorded”?

Practicalities

Recording the telephone call?

- As it will probably not be possible to fill out the template while conducting the interview we recommend you to record the interview.
- Always ask permission to record a telephone call! If you have this permission on tape, then a signed informed consent form is no longer necessary.
- Making an ad verbatim transcription of the recording is not necessary. The recording can however help you to fill in the template correctly and to make a correct interpretation and analysis of the data.

Data validation

Proof reading?

If there is a possibility, we recommend you send the filled out questionnaire to the interviewee for proof reading. In this way the interpretation made by the interviewer is validated.

However

- This implies that the interviewee understands English
- Beware that this might considerably slow down the process of finishing the LTR

TIMING

- The final versions of the 12 LTRs of your institute will be due on the 28th of June
- In the meantime you can always contact the T3.1 team with questions.
- We would also like you to report on your progress for that purpose we will organise bilateral skype calls!
- And finally...
- The allowable word counts for the answers to the questions have deliberately been kept very low. So make every word count! Focus on the most relevant information and do not include speculative information.